

EVALUATION OF AGGREGATE STABILITY AND HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY OF SOILS DERIVED FROM DIFFERENT PARENT MATERIALS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, SOUTH SOUTH NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to evaluate aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity of soils derived from freshwater alluvium (FWA), coastal plain sand (CPS) and sandstone (SDS) in Akwa Ibom State, South-South Nigeria. Seventy-two core and composite soil samples obtained at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm depths from six locations representing the parent materials were analyzed by standard methods to determine their physical/chemical properties, mean weight diameter (MWD), microaggregate stability and Ksat. Results showed FWA/SDS soils were sandy loam and sandy clay loam, while CPS soils were

loamy sand and sandy loam at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm depths respectively. Bulk densities ₃

(1.42 – 1.58 g/cm³) were all low; organic matter (1.21 – 1.99%) was low in CPS/SDS soils, but high (3.10 – 4.02%) in FWA soils. Average MWD values for FWA, SDS and CPS soils

at 0 – 20 cm sampling depth were 0.349, 0.184 and 0.180 mm; whereas they were 0.288, 0.221 and 0.271 mm at 20 – 40 cm depth respectively. Average clay dispersion ratios for FWA, CPS and SDS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth were 27.97, 28.51 and 29.16%; whereas they were 26.13, 26.95 and 28.19% at 20 – 40 cm depth respectively. Average Ksat values for FWA, CPS and SDS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth were 25.27, 30.49 and 26.01 cm/hr; whereas they were 16.36, 17.50 and 16.94 cm/hr at 0 – 40 cm depth respectively. Regular

applications of manure and adoption of other conservation measures were recommended. (2015). Among the factors influencing its

INTRODUCTION

Soil is a fundamental component of the earth's terrestrial ecosystems that provides a medium for growth and productivity of plants and animals, biogeochemical cycling, air and water quality regulation, filtering and buffering of pollutants and habitation for many species of organisms, making it a critical resource for maintaining life on earth (Brady & Weil, 2012., FAO,

evolution and properties is the material from which it is formed, usually referred to as parent material. It can be the sedentary/residual material produced in situ from the weathering of a bedrock of igneous, sedimentary or metamorphic origin, unconsolidated sediments transported and deposited by geologic agents or organic deposits that have been

Keywords: Aggregate stability, saturated hydraulic conductivity, freshwater alluvium, coastal plain sands, sandstone.

accumulated particularly in low-lying areas under anaerobic conditions (FAO, 2006; Esu, 2010). Parent materials generally influence soil properties as they weather to form soils (Lal & Stewart, 2012; Oguike *et al.*, 2019). (FAO, 2006; Esu, 2010).

Soil aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity are among soil physical properties that determine soil health and productivity. While aggregate stability measures the ability of a soil to resist disintegration when exposed to erosion or any other external stress and is important for gaseous exchange, aeration, infiltration, drainage and water storage in soil; hydraulic conductivity measures the ability of a soil to transmit water under saturated or unsaturated conditions and is important for understanding soil water balance, estimating groundwater recharge, determining irrigation rates and predicting erosion, waterlogging and leaching (Brady & Weil, 2012; Bronick & Lal, 2015; Campbell *et al.*, 2023).

Soil aggregates are clumps of primary soil particles (sand, silt and clay) formed by the flocculation and cementation processes in soils. They are the basic units of soil structure that help create soil pores making water and air movements possible (Brady & Weil, 2012). Those that are less than 0.25 mm in size are categorized as microaggregates and their formation and stability are mostly dependent on soil clay mineralogy, monovalent/polyvalent cations ratio and organic matter and are more stable (Chenu *et al.*, 2000., Duchicela *et al.*, 2012., Portela *et al.*, 2012); whereas those that are greater than 0.25 mm are categorized as macroaggregates and their formation and stability mostly depend on soil organic matter and are less stable (Nimmo & Perkins, 2002., Yan *et al.*,

2009). Slaking and dispersion are the main mechanisms of disintegration for macroaggregates and microaggregates respectively (Udom & Anozie, 2018). A most widely used parameter for assessing soil macroaggregate stability is the mean weight diameter (MWD), defined as the sum of the products of aggregate fractions and mean diameter of aggregate size classes, and higher values indicate higher stability (Oguike *et al.*, 2019; Franzlubbers, 2022); while the dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion index (CDI) and clay flocculation index (CFI) are some of the parameters or indices used for assessing soil microaggregate stability (Igwe & Obalum, 2013). Higher DR and CDI values indicate lower stability, whereas higher CFI and ASC values indicate greater stability (Igwe & Nwokocha, 2006). The MWD values of 0.28 to 20.10 mm and the DR, CDI, CFI and ASC values of 21.20 to 37.30%, 12.80 to 46.09%, 50.00 to 80.11% and 9.00 to 50.00% have been respectively reported for soils in southern Nigeria (Udom & Anozie, 2018., Oguike *et al.*, 2019., Okoror *et al.*, 2024).

Soil hydraulic conductivity measured in the laboratory is designated as saturated K (Ksat); while the one measured in the field is designated as unsaturated K (Kunsat) (Campbell *et al.*, 2023). Past researchers (Udom & Anozike, 2018., Ogban and Ibitt, 2018., Okoror *et al.*, 2024) have reported -3.

Ksat values of 4.30 cmhr to 34.30 cmhr for soils in some parts of southern Nigeria. According to them, the high saturated hydraulic conductivity values reflected the loose and porous nature of the soils. Most soils in Nigeria are structurally fragile and unstable due to their sandy nature and low organic matter contents as well as the

extreme weather and climatic conditions of the country and inappropriate land use management practices, particularly in areas where intensive tillage and cultivation have been practised regularly (Ogban & Ibitt, 2018; Okoror *et al.*, 2024). The adverse effects of all these have been reported including low fertility and agricultural productivity and increased susceptibility to water erosion, leaching and crusting (Oguike *et al.*, 2019., Okoror *et al.*, 2024). Problems of this nature may be difficult to solve without adequate knowledge of aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity which have direct relationships with crop growth and yields due to their influences on water infiltration, aeration, water movement and water availability in soils. Such knowledge is useful in developing best soil and water management strategies for optimum crop and animal production and in designing effective effluents disposal systems (Ogban & Ibitt, 2018).

Although similar studies have been done before in the present study area by Ogban & Ibitt (2018) and others, information on aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity of soils in the present study locations is scarce. It is believed that the findings and recommendations of this study, coupled with those of past researchers, might help in developing effective soil and water management strategies for optimum crop and animal

production and efficient effluents disposal systems. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to determine some physical and chemical properties of some soils derived from different parent materials in Akwa Ibom State, determine their aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity and evaluate the relationships between the aggregate stability indices and the physical/chemical properties of the studied soils.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, located between latitudes 4°32' and 5°33'N and longitudes 7°25' and 8°25'E. The area has the tropical monsoon climate with a longer wet season (April – October) and is characterized by the mean annual rainfall that varies from about 2,000 mm in the northern parts to about 4,000 mm along the coastline, and a shorter dry season that spans between November and March (NiMet, 2022). Soils in the state are reportedly formed from different parent materials including alluvium, beach sand, coastal plain sand and sandstone (Petters *et al.*, 1989; NGS, 2009). The study locations, soil parent materials and their coordinates are in Table 1.

Table 1: Coordinates and soil parent materials of the sampling locations

Sampling Location	Coordinates/Altitude of Sampling Points	Soil Parent material
Utu Etim Ekpo	04°94'22''N, 007°57'21''E, 61 m	Freshwater alluvium (FWA)
	04°94'58''N, 007°57'56''E, 61 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	04°94'89''N, 007°57'89''E, 61 m	
Ayadehe	05°28'33''N, 007°21'26''E, 52 m	Freshwater alluvium(FWA)
	05°28'33''N, 007°21'57''E, 52 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	05°28'33''N, 007°21'88''E, 52 m	
Obio Akpa	04°57'23''N, 007°44'03''E, 56 m	Coastal Plain Sand(CPS)
	04°57'58''N, 007°44'54''E, 56 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	04°57'97''N, 007°44'87''E, 56 m	
Use Offot	05°01'21''N, 007°58'16''E, 66 m	Coastal Plain Sand(CPS)
	05°01'53''N, 007°58'52''E, 66 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	05°01'86''N, 007°58'93''E, 66 m	
Odoro Ikpe	05°23'28''N, 007°45'04''E, 82 m	Sandstone (SDS)
	05°23'28''N, 007°45'22''E, 82 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	05°23'28''N, 007°45'56''E, 82 m	
Afua	05°18'27''N, 007°54'65''E, 101 m	Sandstone(SDS)
	05°18'27''N, 007°54'77''E, 101 m	Source: (Petters <i>et al.</i> , 1989; NGSA, 2009; Uduak, 2019)
	05°18'27''N, 007°54'89''E, 101 m	

Soil Sample Collection and Processing

A total of seventy-two soil samples obtained at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm depth intervals across the six locations were used for the study. Thirty-six of the soil samples were core samples obtained with core cylinders of known weight and volume, while the rest were composite samples obtained with a hand auger. Ten grab samples were bulked and thoroughly mixed to obtain one composite sample.

Laboratory Analysis

Particle size distribution will be determined by the hydrometer method using the procedure outlined by Udo *et al.* (2009) and Bowen (2023) and the textural classes will be determined with the USDA soil textural triangle. Bulk density was determined by the method of Grossman and Reinsch (2002) and calculation was done as follows:

$$\text{Bulk density (gcm}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Mass of oven-dry soil sample} \times 100}{\text{Volume of soil sample}}$$

Total porosity was determined by the method described by Flint and Flint (2002) and computed using the bulk density value and assumed particle density of 2.65 gcm³ as follows:

$$\text{Total porosity (\%)} = \frac{1 - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Particle density (taken as 2.65 gcm}^3\text{)}}$$

Moisture content was determined gravimetrically as outlined by (Cater, 1993). The mean weight diameter (MWD) used to assess soil macroaggregate stability was determined by the wet sieving method outlined by Kemper & Rosenau and calculated using the following expression: $MWD = \sum xw$, Where MWD is the mean weight diameter, \sum is summation, x is the mean sieve size and w is the mass of the individual soil sample remaining in each

sieve after wet-sieving and oven-drying. Soil samples were passed through the 4.75 mm-mesh sieve and wet-sieved using a nest of sieves of diameter 2, 1, 0.5 and 0.25 mm. The dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion index (CDI), clay flocculation index (CFI) and associated silt and clay (ASC) used to assess soil microaggregate stability were determined by the silt/clay dispersion method and they were calculated as follows (Ogwoke *et al.*, 2019):

$$DR = \frac{\% \text{ Silt} + \% \text{ Clay in water dispersed sample} \times 100}{\% \text{ Silt} + \% \text{ clay in Calgon dispersed samples}}$$

$$CDI = \frac{\% \text{ Clay dispersed in water} \times 100}{\% \text{ Clay dispersed in Calgon}}$$

$$CFI = \frac{\% \text{ Clay dispersed in Calgon} - \% \text{ Clay dispersed in water} \times 100}{\% \text{ Clay dispersed in Calgon}}$$

$$ASC = [\% \text{ Silt} + \% \text{ Clay dispersed in Calgon}] - [\% \text{ Silt} + \% \text{ Clay dispersed in water}]$$

Saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{sat}) was measured by the constant head method using the procedure outlined by Romano and Santini (2002) and calculated using Darcy's equation for vertical flow of liquid as follows:

$$K_{sat} = \frac{Q}{A} \times \frac{L}{\Delta H}$$

Where K_{sat} is the soil saturated hydraulic conductivity, Q is the volume of water flowing through a cross-sectional area, A is the cross-sectional area of the core, T is the elapsed time, L is the core length and ΔH is the hydraulic head difference. Electrical conductivity was determined in a 1:5 soil/water suspension with an electrical conductivity meter using the procedure outlined by (Bowen, 2023). Organic carbon content was determined by the Walkley and Black wet oxidation method outlined by Nelson and Sommers (1996). Soil pH was determined in water at the soil/water ratio of 1:2.5 (Bowen, 2023). Total nitrogen,

available phosphorus, exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) and exchangeable acidity were determined by the macro-Kjeldahl, Bray P1, 1 M neutral NH_4OAc extraction and 1 M KCl titration routine methods outlined by Udo *et al.* (2009). Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and base saturation were determined by calculations using the expressions outlined by Udo *et al.* (2009).

Statistical Analysis

Soil data were statistically analyzed using means and ranges, while the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis was

used to establish and assess the relationships between soil aggregate stability and other soil properties determined during the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION Physical/Chemical Properties of the Soils

The physical properties of the soils are shown in Tables 2 - 4. The mean sand, silt and clay contents of the FWA soils obtained at 0 – 20 cm depth (Table 2) were 715, 86 and 202 g/kg;

Table 2: Physical/Chemical Properties of FWA Soils

Soil Location	Soil depth (cm)	Sand g/kg	Silt g/kg	Clay g/kg	TC	BD g/c	TP %	MC %	OM %
Utu Etim Ekpo	0-200-20	706	82	212	S	1.50	43.4	185.2	4.20
		724	82	190	L	1.54	0	0	4.16
		704	86	200	S	1.50	41.8	180.1	3.98
Ayadehe	0-20	724	106	202	L	1.51	9	6	4.20
		716	84	206	S	1.47	43.4	201.4	3.90
		714	86	200	L	1.52	0	1	4.10
Mean		715	86	202	S	1.5	43.0	200.7	4.09
Utu Etim Ekpo	20-40	672	6	2	S	2	44.5	9	3.21
		606	9	33	SC	1.5	0	194.1	3.11
		656	2	6	L	6	0	6	3.67
Ayadehe	20-40	586	9	30	SC	1.5	42.6	6	3.86
		602	4	0	L	7	43.1	202.1	3.87
		626	9	25	SC	1.5	3	193.9	3.52
Mean		625	6	34	SC	1.53	41.3	196.3	3.54

TC = Textural class, BD = Bulk density, TP = Total porosity, MC = Moisture content, OM = Organic matter.

whereas those recorded for the 20 – 40 cm depth (Table 2) were 608, 85 and 306 g/kg respectively. The mean sand, silt and clay contents of the CPS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth (Table 3) were 845, 54 and 104 g/kg; whereas those recorded at 20 – 40 cm depth (Table 3) were 663, 63 and 274 g/kg respectively. The sand, silt and clay contents of the SDS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth (Table 4) were 721, 103 and 177 g/kg; whereas those recorded for the 20 – 40 cm

depth (Table 4) were 639, 104 and 257 g/kg respectively. Sand dominated the two layers of all the soils studied and decreased in amount with soil depth. Clay followed sand in dominance in all the soils, but increased in amount with soil depth. Silt showed no regular distribution pattern in the FWA soils (Table 2), but decreased with sampling depth in the CPS Use Offot and SDS

42.3	0
0	215.2
41.7	1
4	202.2
	1

Table 3: Physical/Chemical Properties of CPS Soils

Soil Location	Soil depth (cm)	Sand g/kg	Silt g/kg	Clay g/kg	TC	BD g/cm	TP %	MC %	OM %
Obio Akpa	0-20	842	52	106	LS	1.46	44.50	40.12	1.75
		854	42	114	LS	1.42	46.40	42.10	1.91
		846	46	108	LS	1.51	43.00	37.61	1.98
Use Offot	0-20	854	62	104	LS	1.47	44.50	40.20	1.86
		842	56	102	LS	1.50	43.40	38.11	1.80
		834	66	100	LS	1.48	43.40	36.10	1.99
Mean		845	54	106		1.47	44.20	39.00	1.88
Obio Akpa	20-40	676	64	260	SL	1.47	44.50	42.14	1.62
		666	42	292	SL	1.44	46.40	43.52	1.60
		652	62	286	SL	1.53	43.00	38.06	1.40
Use Offot	20-40	642	66	292	SL	1.51	46.40	41.22	1.21
		666	72	262	SL	1.52	44.50	39.62	1.72
		676	72	252	SL	1.50	43.40	38.41	1.53
Mean		663	63	274		1.54	44.70	40.50	1.51

TC = Textural class, BD = Bulk density, TP = Total porosity, MC = Moisture content, OM = Organic matter.

Odoro Ikpe soils. The FWA and SDS soils exhibited sandy loam and sandy clay loam textures at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm respectively. The CPS soils had loamy sand and sandy loam textures at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm depths respectively. The dominance of sand in each of the soil categories studied could be due to the sandy nature of the three parent materials; whereas the increasing clay contents with sampling depth could be an indication of eluviation and illuviation, which are two fundamental pedogenic processes occurring in virtually all soils (Mahajan, 2023). The bulk densities (BD) of the FWA, CPS and SDS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth (Tables 2 - 4) ranged from 1.42 g/cm to 1.55 g/cm with the mean values of 1.52, 1.47 and 1.50 g/cm; whereas at 20 – 40 cm depth, the bulk densities ranged from 1.44 g/cm to 1.58 g/cm with the mean values of 1.53, 1.54 and 1.54 g/cm respectively. The BD of virtually

all the soils were higher at 20 – 40 cm depth and were within the 1.00 - 1.60 g/cm³ normal range for productive agricultural soils reported by Acquah (2005), suggesting no compaction. Total porosity (TP) of all the soils ranged from 40.40% to 46.50% at both depths (Table 2 - 4). At both depths, the mean TP varied in the order: CPS > SDS > FWA and was at least moderate for all the soils. The TP of virtually all the FWA soils (Table 2) was higher at 0 – 20 cm depth, whereas the TP of the CPS/SDS soils (Table 3 - 4) showed no regular distribution pattern. The moisture contents (MC) of all the soils ranged from 31.25% to 215.21% and varied in the order at both depths: FWA > SDS > CPS. The MC of virtually all the soils studied was higher at 20 – 40 cm which could be due to higher clay contents. The relatively high MC of the FWA soils could be due to their poor drainage conditions, which could reduce macroaggregate stability especially and microbial activity (Brady & Weil, 2012).

The organic matter contents (OM) (Tables 2 - 4) varied from low (1.21 – 1.99%) in the CPS/SDS soils to high (3.11 – 4.21%) in the FWA soils (FPDD, 1990). The low status of organic matter in the CPS/SDS soils could be an indication of low inputs and high rates

of organic matter decomposition, which could negatively affect aggregate formation and stability, porosity, bulk density, water holding, hydraulic properties, nutrient retention, fertility and

Table 4: Physical/Chemical Properties of SDSSoils

Soil Location	Soil depth (cm)	Sand g/kg	Silt g/kg	Clay g/kg	TC	BD g/cm	TP %	MC %	OM %
Oodoro Ikpe	0-20	702	104	174	SL	1.55	44.50	35.10	1.62
		704	112	186	SL	1.53	43.40	31.42	1.71
		736	94	170	SL	1.55	44.20	31.25	1.98
Afua	0-20	706	102	192	SL	1.42	41.40	32.33	1.68
		732	112	156	SL	1.47	44.30	34.16	1.70
		724	94	182	SL	1.48	43.40	33.66	1.91
Mean		721	103	177		1.50	43.53	33.00	1.77
Oodoro Ikpe	20-40	634	82	284	SCL	1.57	40.75	35.26	1.50
		642	106	252	SCL	1.54	41.89	32.16	1.62
		642	102	256	SCL	1.57	40.75	31.33	1.52
Afua	20-40	642	116	242	SCL	1.53	42.30	33.14	1.47
		636	106	258	SCL	1.52	42.60	34.40	1.61
		636	112	252	SCL	1.51	43.00	33.71	1.70
Mean		639	104	257		1.54	41.88	33.33	1.57

TC = Textural class, BD = Bulk density, TP = Total porosity, MC = Moisture content, OM = Organic matter.

productivity of the soils; whereas ; whereas the high status of organic matter in the FWA soils may be due to high accumulation and slow decomposition of organic materials due to the poor drainage conditions of the soils (Brady & Weil, 2012). Increasing the organic matter status of the soils through regular applications of manure and even biochar can help improve the CPS/SDS soils and their productivity (Brady & Weil, 2012). The results agree with Ibia, 2012., Uduak et al., 2012., Uduak et al., 2014; Ekong & Uduak., 2015; Uduak et al., 2017).

Aggregate Stability and Hydraulic Conductivity of the Soils

The results of aggregate stability and hydraulic conductivity measurements are shown in Tables 5 - 7. At the 0 – 20 cm sampling depth (Tables 5 - 7), the mean weight diameter (MWD) of FWA, CPS and SDS soils ranged from 0.125 mm to 0.421 mm, 0.220 mm to 0.420 mm and 0.142 mm to 0.214 mm with the mean values of 0.349, 0.180 and 0.184 mm; whereas at the 0 – 20 cm sampling depth (Tables 5 - 7), it ranged from 0.120 mm to 0.412 mm, 0.220 mm to 0.410 mm and 0.101 mm to 0.310 mm with

the mean values of 0.288, 0.271 and 0.221 mm respectively. About 50% of the FWA and CPS soils recorded higher MWD values at the 0 – 20 cm sampling depth, whereas most of the SDS soils (about 66%) recorded higher MWD at the 20 – 40 cm sampling depth. In all, the mean MWD values indicated highest and lowest macroaggregate stability in FWA and CPS soils at the 0 – 20 cm depth and highest and lowest macroaggregate stability in FWA and SDS soils at the 20 – 40 cm depth which could be due to differences in clay and organic matter contents of the soil categories.

The dispersion ratio (DR), clay dispersion

ratio (CDR), clay flocculation index (CFI) and associated silt and clay (ASC) used in assessing the microaggregate stability of the soils ranged from 26.30% to 31.16%, 25/81% to 30.00%, 62.01% to 72.16% and 30.14% to 38.14% at the 0 – 20 cm sampling depth of the FWA soils (Table 5) with the mean values of 29.09, 27.97, 78.06 and 33.77% respectively; whereas the DR, CDR, CFI and ASC used in assessing the microaggregate stability of the FWA soils at the 20 – 40 cm sampling depth (Table 5) ranged from 24.12% to 29.14%, 24.01% to 28.16%, 60.16% to 70.51% and 30.60% to 37.16% with the mean values of 27.15, 26.13, 65.12 and 32.90% respectively. Virtually all the DR, CDI, CFI

Table 5: Aggregate stability indices and Ksat of FWA soils

Soil Location	Soil Depth (cm)	MWD (mm)	DR (%)	CDR (%)	CFI (%)	ASC (%)	Ksat cm/hr
Utu Etim Ekpo	0–20	0.125	26.3	25.81	72.16	35.2	26.01
		0.420	0	28.42	71.14	2	24.33
		0.410	30.1	30.00	62.01	36.1	23.16
Ayadehe	0–20	0.421	1	26.32	68.12	4	24.34
		0.310	20.1	28.11	71.10	31.6	22.17
		0.410	2	29.16	62.72	2	31.60
Mean		0.349	29.09	27.97	78.06	33.77	25.27
Utu Etim Ekpo	20–40	0.14	24.1	24.01	70.11	33.1	23.10
		1	28.7	26.31	68.24	38.1	21.11
		0.22	28.2	28.16	61.12	33.2	10.12
Ayadehe	20–40	0	31.1	24.86	60.57	30.1	12.16
		0.23	29.1	26.17	70.51	30.6	9.15
		1	4	27.28	60.16	0	22.51
Mean		0.288	27.15	26.13	65.12	32.90	16.36

MWD_w = Wet mean weight diameter, DR = Dispersion ratio, CDR = Clay dispersion ratio, CFI = Clay flocculation index, ASC = Associated silt + clay

and ASC values recorded for the FWA soils were higher at the 0 – 20 cm sampling depth. The DR, CDR, CFI and ASC used in assessing the microaggregate stability of

the CPS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth (Table 6) ranged from 26.16% to 33.16%, 25.14% to 32.10%, 58.33% to 63.16%

Table 6: Aggregate stability indices and Ksat of CPS soils

Soil Location	Soil depth (cm)	MWD (mm)	DR (%)	CDR (%)	CFI (%)	ASC (%)	Ksat cm/hr
Obio Akpa	0–20	0.321	26.16	25.14	61.22	36.20	31.21
		0.310	29.30	27.22	60.41	33.11	30.66
		0.420	32.15	32.10	63.16	34.15	28.16
Use Offot	0–20	0.220	33.16	30.10	60.31	28.28	29.60
		0.320	30.22	29.27	58.33	30.15	26.18
		0.270	28.61	27.22	61.13	36.12	37.10
Mean		0.180	29.93	28.51	60.76	33.00	30.49
Obio Akpa	20–40	0.220	26.01	25.11	78.24	35.10	21.40
		0.410	28.12	26.14	76.14	32.12	19.16
		0.311	30.28	30.01	71.61	33.42	12.16
Use Offot	20–40	0.321	31.12	28.16	60.57	28.11	18.17
		0.312	28.14	26.14	77.33	30.00	11.11
		0.280	27.17	26.16	76.88	38.14	23.00
Mean		0.271	29.47	26.95	59.71	32.82	17.50

MWD_w = Wet mean weight diameter, DR = Dispersion ratio, CDR = Clay dispersion ratio, CFI = Clay flocculation index, ASC = Associated silt + clay.

and 28.28% to 36.12% with the mean values of 29.93, 28.51, 60.76 and 33.00%; whereas those used in assessing the microaggregate stability of the CPS soils at 20–40 cm depth (Table 6) ranged from 26.01% to 31.12%, 25.11% to 30.01%, 58.14% to 60.30% and 28.11% to 38.14% with the mean values of 29.47, 26.95, 59.71 and 32.82% respectively. All the DR, CDR, CFI and ASC values recorded for the CPS soils were higher at 0–20 cm depth which could be due to higher clay contents at that soil layer. The DR, CDR, CFI and ASC used

in assessing the microaggregate stability of the SDS soils at 0–20 cm depth (Table 7) ranged from 28.11% to 33.01%, 26.40% to 31.22%, 60.57% to 78.24% and 34.21% to 38.11% with the mean values of 30.65, 29.16, 72.12 and 36.13%; whereas those used in assessing the microaggregate stability of the SDS soils at 20–40 cm depth (Table 7) ranged from 26.90% to 32.10%, 26.87% to 29.22%, 60.15% to 78.21% and 30.14% to 37.10% with the mean values of 29.57, 28.19, 72.18 and 34.29% respectively.

Table 7: Aggregate stability indices and K_{sat} of SDS soils

Soil Location	Soil depth (cm)	MWD (mm)	DR (%)	CDR (%)	CFI (%)	ASC (%)	K _{sat} (cm/hr)
OdoroIkpe	0-20	0.142	30.18	28.16	75.21	38.11	28.61
		0.171	32.11	30.14	73.17	36.68	22.01
		0.214	28.11	26.40	70.42	37.20	28.30
Afua	0-20	0.230	33.01	31.22	60.57	34.21	24.16
		0.212	29.11	28.66	77.33	34.25	23.25
		0.132	31.40	30.40	76.88	36.32	20.15
Mean		0.184	30.65	29.16	72.12	36.13	26.01
Odoro Ikpe	20-40	0.140	28.16	27.12	75.21	35.01	17.01
		0.213	31.14	29.22	73.17	36.17	15.81
		0.310	26.90	27.20	70.42	33.16	17.72
Afua	20-40	0.311	32.10	30.62	60.15	30.14	9.51
		0.131	28.88	26.86	78.21	34.16	21.11
		0.221	30.22	28.12	75.92		
Mean		0.221	29.57	28.19	72.18	34.29	16.94

MWD_w = Wet mean weight diameter, DR = Dispersion ratio, CDR = Clay dispersion ratio, CFI = Clay flocculation index, ASC = Associated silt +clay

The K_{sat} values recorded for the FWA, CPS and SDS soils at 0 – 20 cm depth (Tables 5 - 7) ranged from 22.17 to 31.60 cm/hr, 26.18 to 37.10 cm/hr and 22.01 to 30.16 cm/hr with the mean values of 25.27, 30.49 and 26.01 cm/hr; whereas those recorded for the soils at 20 – 40 cm depth (Tables 5 - 7) ranged from 9.15 to 23.10 cm/hr, 11.11 to 23.00 cm/hr and 9.51 to 21.11 cm/hr with the mean values of 16.36, 17.50 and 16.94 cm/hr respectively. The K_{sat} values recorded for the three soil categories studied were higher at 0 – 20 cm depth. In comparison, the CPS soils recorded the highest mean K_{sat} values at both depths, followed by the SDS and FWA soils in that order. The results agree with those reported by some past reports including Udom & Anozie (2018) and Ogban & Ibitt (2018). The high K_{sat} values recorded for the soils could be due to the sandy nature of the soils. According to USDA (2014), sandy soils

have high to very high hydraulic conductivities ranging 5-20 cmh⁻¹ because of their relatively large pore spaces.

CONCLUSION

Sand dominated the two layers of all the soils studied and decreased in amount with sampling depth. Clay followed sand in dominance in all the soils and increased in amount with soil depth. Silt showed no regular distribution pattern in the FWA soils, but decreased with sampling depth in the CPS Use Offot and SDS Odoro Ikpe soils. The FWA and SDS soils exhibited sandy loam and sandy clay loam textures at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm respectively. The BD values recorded for all the soils were within the 1.00 - 1.60 g/cm³ normal range for productive agricultural soils. The mean total porosity varied in the order: CPS > SDS > FWA and was at least moderate for all the soils. The moisture contents (MC) of

all the soils varied in the order at both depths: FWA > SDS > CPS. The MC of virtually all the soils studied was higher at 20 – 40 cm. The organic matter contents (OM) contents of CPS/SDS soils were low; whereas those of FWA soils were high.

The average MWD recorded for each sampling depth of FWA soils was the highest indicating the highest macroaggregate stability of the soils; whereas that recorded for each sampling depth of CPS and SDS soils was the lowest at 0 – 20 cm and 20 – 40 cm depths respectively. At both sampling depths, SDS

soils recorded the highest average DR/CDR indicating the lowest microaggregate stability, while FWA soils recorded the lowest DR/CDR indicating the highest microaggregate stability. At both sampling depths, CPS soils recorded the highest average Ksat value, while FWA soils recorded the lowest Ksat value. Regular applications of manure and biochar as well as occasional applications of appropriate inorganic/organomineral fertilizers and adoption of erosion control and conservation tillage practices were recommended.

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